

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Fig. S1 - Envelopes of potential temperature, θ , and salinity, s , versus depth, z , for sites across the North Atlantic Ocean and Nordic Seas (site abbreviations as defined in Fig. 2). Climatological mean depth profiles are shown (dash-dotted lines) and envelope bounds (solid lines) represent mean values $\pm$ 2 SDs. Sites below the broken line (i.e. DAV, DEN, and FAR) were not included in the θ - s curvature analysis (see main text).

Fig. S1 – (continued)

Fig. S1 – (continued)

Fig. S1 – (continued)

Fig. S2 – Potential temperature–salinity (θ - s) diagrams for sites across the North Atlantic Ocean and Nordic Seas (site abbreviations as defined in Fig. 2). Dash-dotted lines are climatological mean curves used in the curvature analysis. DAV, DEN, and FAR sites are not included, for reasons explained in the main text. Note the different scales applied for θ , s , and depth, z , from panel to panel.

Fig. S2 – (continued)

Fig. S2 – (continued)

Fig. S2 – (continued)

Table S1 – Full names relating to water mass abbreviations used in this study, and comments on water mass distributions and/or origins.

Abbreviation	Full name	Comment
(C)ArW	(Canadian) Arctic Water	Arctic Ocean outflow to Baffin Bay through the Canadian Arctic Archipelago.
(IC)IrAW	(Irminger Current) Irminger Atlantic Water	In this study, intended to represent Irminger Sea water carried northwards through the Denmark Strait by the North Icelandic Irminger Current (NIIC).
(NS)ArW	(Nordic Seas) Arctic Water	Water from the basins of the Nordic Seas contributing to DSOW via the North Icelandic Jet (NIJ).
(WG)IrAW	(West Greenland) Irminger Atlantic Water	Component of the northwards-flowing West Greenland Current (WGC), concentrated on the continental slope and carrying water from the Irminger Sea.
ArIW	Arctic Intermediate Water	Intermediate waters formed in the convective gyres of the Greenland and Iceland Seas or (in the case of the Norwegian Sea) fed by the advection of other intermediate waters (see NwArIW).
ArODW	Arctic Ocean Deep Water	Bracket term incorporating deep waters of the Arctic (Polar) Ocean (see EBDW and CBDW).
ArSW	Arctic Surface Water	Surface waters of the Nordic Seas (particularly the Greenland and Iceland Seas) not otherwise specified.
BBDW	Baffin Bay Deep Water	Deep water found in Baffin Bay, the origin/formation of which is still debated.
CBDW	Canadian Basin Deep Water	Deep water in the Canadian Basin of the Arctic Ocean; originates largely from the Eurasian Basin, where it was modified (to become warmer and more saline) by interactions with shelf plumes and Atlantic-derived water.
DSOW	Denmark Strait Overflow Water	Dense water overflowing the sill of the Denmark Strait into the deep North Atlantic. Sources are the East Greenland Current (EGC) and (NS)ArW carried by the North Icelandic Jet (NIJ). DSOW forms the densest component of North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW) and contributes significantly to the Deep Western Boundary Current (DWBC).
EBDW	Eurasian Basin Deep Water	Deep water in the Eurasian Basin of the Arctic Ocean; a mixture of dense plumes formed on the Arctic Ocean shelves and deep water from the Nordic Seas entering through the Fram Strait.
ENACW	East North Atlantic Central Water	Characterised by a nearly straight line in θ - s diagrams, ENACW occupies the upper layer in the Northeast Atlantic and is formed by winter mixing and subduction over an area from the northeast Azores to the European margin, bounded by the North Atlantic Current (NAC) and Azores Current (AC).

FSAW	Fram Strait Atlantic Water	Atlantic-origin water entering the Nansen Basin of the Arctic Ocean via the Fram Strait / West Spitsbergen Current (WSC).
GDW	Greenland Sea Deep Water	Deep water mass historically formed by deep winter convection in the Greenland Sea (NB: convective activity in the Greenland Sea has changed in recent decades and ArODW is having a greater influence).
GFZW	Gibbs Fracture Zone Water	Deep water mass entering the western North Atlantic largely through the Charlie-Gibbs Fracture Zone (CGFZ). GFZW describes the admixture of ISOW and NEADW, which contributes to the deep waters and boundary currents of the Northwest Atlantic.
ISOW	Iceland-Scotland Overflow Water	Dense water flowing from the Norwegian Sea into the North Atlantic over the Iceland-Scotland Ridge and through Faroe Bank Channel.
IW	Intermediate Water	Intermediate water mass above Charlie-Gibbs Fracture Zone (CGFZ), as identified in Racapé et al. (2019).
LDW (AABW)	Lower Deep Water (Antarctic Bottom Water)	Abyssal water mass found throughout the Northeast Atlantic, derived from Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) entering the area at the Vema and Romanche Fracture Zones. AABW is formed by deep convection associated with sea ice formation in the Ross and Weddell Seas.
LSLW	Labrador Slope Water	A water mass found along the Newfoundland/Scotian Slopes, flowing to the southwest as a component of the Labrador Current (LC). It is found shoreward of and beneath WSW (see below).
LSW	Labrador Sea Water	Water mass formed in the Labrador Sea by deep convection caused by winter surface cooling. It is found at mid-depths nearly everywhere in the northern North Atlantic, but extends further south along the western boundary of the North Atlantic.
MW	Mediterranean Water	Intermediate water mass formed in the Gulf of Cádiz as the outflow of sub-surface Mediterranean water (Mediterranean Overflow Water; MOW) over the sill of the Strait of Gibraltar entrains ENACW in particular. MW spreads at intermediate depths to the north, along the western European margin, and west, towards the Azores (primarily as anticyclonic eddies, or ‘meddies’).
NEADW	Northeast Atlantic Deep Water	A deep water mass in the Northeast Atlantic (but also influencing the north-western basins), defined by the mixing of four water types (ISOW, LSW, MW, and LDW). In the Northeast Atlantic, the core of NEADW is found beneath LSW and above LDW, and generally moves southwards (although it also crosses the Mid-Atlantic Ridge heading west at the Charlie-Gibbs Fracture Zone (CGFZ)).

NwArIW	Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water	ArIW beneath the upper Atlantic-derived layer (i.e. NwAW) in the Norwegian Sea. Unlike ArIW in the Iceland and Greenland Seas, NwArIW is not formed by convection locally, but is rather fed by advection of adjacent intermediate waters. NwArIW forms a major component of ISOW.
NwAW	Norwegian Sea Atlantic Water	Upper layer waters of the various branches of the Norwegian Atlantic Current in the Norwegian Sea.
NwDW	Norwegian Sea Deep Water	Deep water mass of the Norwegian Sea; a mixture of ArODW and GDW.
PW	Polar Water	Cold, fresh upper water masses from the Arctic Ocean, influenced there by river runoff, positive net precipitation, relatively fresh Pacific inflow, and seasonal ice melt. PW leaves the Arctic Ocean travelling equatorward (e.g. in the East Greenland Current (EGC)).
RAW	Re-circulating Atlantic Water	Atlantic water from the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) that has re-circulated in the Fram Strait area and submerged beneath less dense PW to the west to augment the East Greenland Current (EGC). This is joined in the EGC by (amongst other components) Atlantic water that has been modified inside the Arctic Ocean (Modified Atlantic Water; MAW), but we do not differentiate between these 2 Atlantic water masses in the present work.
SPMW	Subpolar Mode Water	Subpolar Mode Waters are thick, near-surface layers in the sub-polar North Atlantic with almost vertically uniform properties. SPMWs are associated with the warm sides of the main branches of the North Atlantic Current (NAC)/subpolar gyre.
UPDW	Upper Polar Deep Water	Water mass originating in the Arctic Ocean, where it is found between the upper, Atlantic-derived layer and ArODW. In the Canadian Basin, it is the product of shelf-slope convection. In the Eurasian Basin, it is fed by colder, less saline Atlantic water inflow from the Barents Sea at intermediate depths.
WSW	Warm Slope Water	Sub-surface water over the Scotian Slope. It is the product of mixing between the Gulf Stream, North Atlantic Central Water (NACW), and coastal (shelf) waters, and flows to the northeast, adjacent to the Gulf Stream and offshore relative to LSLW.

Table S2 – Literature sources consulted when interpreting site-specific water mass structure from the potential temperature-salinity (θ - s) diagrams shown in Figure A1 (above the dash-dotted line) and Figure 6 (below the dash-dotted line). Full references are provided at the end of the supplementary material.

Site name	Abbreviation	Literature source(s) for water mass interpretation
Berthois Spur	BER	Pollard et al. 1996; Lavín et al. 2004; González-Pola et al. 2005; Porter et al. 2016
Bill Bailey Bank	BBB	Harvey 1982; Turrell and Sherwin 2003; Johnson et al. 2010
Central Mohn's Ridge	MOHN	Swift and Aagaard 1981; Blindheim and Rey 2004; Le Moine Bauer et al. 2018
Chaucer Seamount	CHAU	Tychensky et al. 1998; Sjøiland et al. 2008; Palma et al. 2012; Caldeira and Reis 2017
East Greenland Shelf	EGRN	Rudels et al. 2002; Amon et al. 2003; Langehaug and Falck 2012
Flemish Cap	FLEM	Lee and Ellett 1967; Kieke and Rhein 2006; van Sebille et al. 2011
Gulf of Cadiz	GoC	Alves et al. 2011; Carracedo et al. 2012; Carracedo et al. 2016
Gully Canyon	GUL	Greenan et al. 2014; MacIsaac et al. 2014; Dever et al. 2016; Filippova et al. 2017
Icelandic Plateau	ICEP	Malmberg et al. 1996; Buch et al. 1996; Blindheim and Østerhus 2005
Jan Mayen Fracture Zone	JMFZ	Buch et al. 1996; Rudels et al. 2003; Mork et al. 2014
Jan Mayen Ridge	JMR	Buch et al. 1996; Rudels et al. 2003; Mork et al. 2014
Minia Seamount / Charlie-Gibbs Fracture Zone	MIN	Racapé et al. 2019
Newfoundland-Labrador Slope	NEW	Lee and Ellett 1967; Kieke and Rhein 2006; van Sebille et al. 2011
North Labrador Sea	NLAB	Lee and Ellett 1967; Kieke and Rhein 2006; van Sebille et al. 2011
North Norwegian Shelf	NNOR	Buhl-Mortensen et al. 2012
North of Svalbard	NSVAL	Schauer et al. 1997; Cokelet et al. 2008; Rudels et al. 2013; Våge et al. 2016; Pérez-Hernández et al. 2017
Northeast Iceland Shelf	NEIS	Read and Pollard 1992
Porcupine Bank / Malin Slope	POR	McGrath et al. 2012

Reykjanes Ridge	REYK	Yashayaev et al. 2007; Kanzow and Zenk 2014; Castrillejo et al. 2018; Fröb et al. 2018; Petit 2018
Rockall Bank	ROCK	McGrath et al. 2012
Rosemary Bank	ROSE	Johnson et al. 2010
Schulz Bank	SHLZ	Roberts et al. 2018
Shetland Islands	SHET	Hansen and Østerhus 2000; McKenna et al. 2016
South of Greenland	SGRN	Kieke and Rhein 2006; de Jong et al. 2009; Castrillejo et al. 2018
South of Svalbard	SSVAL	Langehaug and Falck 2012
West Labrador Sea	WLAB	Lee and Ellett 1967; Kieke and Rhein 2006; van Sebille et al. 2011
West of Svalbard	WSVAL	Langehaug and Falck 2012
Western Barents Sea	WBAR	Buhl-Mortensen et al. 2012; Oziel et al. 2016

Davis Strait	DAV	Tang et al. 2004; Azetsu-Scott et al. 2012
Denmark Strait	DEN	Harden et al. 2016; Mastropole et al. 2017

References (water mass interpretation – see Table S2)

- Alves JMR, Carton X, Ambar I (2011) Hydrological structure, circulation and water mass transport in the Gulf of Cadiz. *Int J Geosci* 2:432–456.
- Amon RMW, Budéus G, Meon B (2003) Dissolved organic carbon distribution and origin in the Nordic Seas: Exchanges with the Arctic Ocean and the North Atlantic. *J Geophys Res* 108:3221.
- Azetsu-Scott K, Petrie B, Yeats P, Lee C (2012) Composition and fluxes of freshwater through Davis Strait using multiple chemical tracers. *J Geophys Res* 117:C12011.
- Blindheim J, Østerhus S (2005) The Nordic Seas, main oceanographic features. In: *The Nordic Seas: An Integrated Perspective - Oceanography, Climatology, Biogeochemistry, and Modeling*. Drange H, Dokken T, Furevik T, Gerdes R, Berger W (eds) American Geophysical Union, Washington DC, p 11–37
- Blindheim J, Rey F (2004) Water-mass formation and distribution in the Nordic Seas during the 1990s. *ICES J Mar Sci* 61:846–863.
- Buch E, Malmberg S-A, Kristmannsson SS (1996) Arctic Ocean deep water masses in the western Iceland Sea. *J Geophys Res* 101:11,965-11,973.

- Buhl-Mortensen L, Bøe R, Dolan MFJ, Buhl-Mortensen P, Thorsnes T, Elvenes S, Hodnesdal H (2012) Banks, troughs, and canyons on the continental margin off Lofoten, Vesterålen, and Troms, Norway. In: *Seafloor geomorphology as benthic habitat*. Elsevier, p 703–715
- Caldeira RMA, Reis JC (2017) The Azores Confluence Zone. *Front Mar Sci* 4:37.
- Carracedo LI, Pardo PC, Flecha S, Pérez FF (2016) On the Mediterranean Water composition. *J Phys Oceanogr* 46:1339–1358.
- Carracedo LI, Pardo PC, Villaceros-Robineau N, De la Granda F, Gilcoto M, Pérez FF (2012) Temporal changes in the water mass distribution and transports along the 20° W CAIBOX section (NE Atlantic). *Ciencias Mar* 38:263–286.
- Castrillejo M, Casacuberta N, Christl M, Vockenhuber C, Synal H-A, García-Ibáñez MI, Lherminier P, Sarthou G, Garcia-Orellana J, Masqué P (2018) Tracing water masses with 129 I and 236 U in the subpolar North Atlantic along the GEOTRACES GA01 section. *Biogeosciences* 15:5545–5564.
- Cokelet ED, Tervalon N, Bellingham JG (2008) Hydrography of the West Spitsbergen Current, Svalbard Branch: Autumn 2001. *J Geophys Res* 113:C01006.
- Dever M, Hebert D, Greenan BJW, Sheng J, Smith PC (2016) Hydrography and coastal circulation along the Halifax Line and the connections with the Gulf of St. Lawrence. *Atmosphere-Ocean* 54:199–217.
- Filippova A, Frank M, Kienast M, Rickli J, Hathorne E, Yashayaev IM, Pahnke K (2017) Water mass circulation and weathering inputs in the Labrador Sea based on coupled Hf–Nd isotope compositions and rare earth element distributions. *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 199:164–184.
- Fröb F, Olsen A, Pérez FF, García-Ibáñez MI, Jeansson E, Omar A, Lauvset SK (2018) Inorganic carbon and water masses in the Irminger Sea since 1991. *Biogeosciences* 15:51–72.
- González-Pola C, Lavín A, Vargas-Yáñez M (2005) Intense warming and salinity modification of intermediate water masses in the southeastern corner of the Bay of Biscay for the period 1992–2003. *J Geophys Res* 110:C05020.
- Greenan BJW, Petrie BD, Cardoso DA (2014) Mean circulation and high-frequency flow amplification in the Sable Gully. *Deep Sea Res Part II Top Stud Oceanogr* 104:20–34.
- Hansen B, Østerhus S (2000) North Atlantic-Nordic Seas exchanges. *Prog Oceanogr* 45:109–208.
- Harden BE, Pickart RS, Valdimarsson H, Våge K, de Steur L, Richards C, Bahr F, Torres D, Børve E, Jónsson S, Macrander A, Østerhus S, Håvik L, Hattermann T (2016) Upstream sources of the Denmark Strait Overflow: Observations from a high-resolution mooring array. *Deep Sea Res Part I Oceanogr Res Pap* 112:94–112.
- Harvey J (1982) θ -S relationships and water masses in the eastern North Atlantic. *Deep Sea Res Part A, Oceanogr Res Pap* 29:1021–1033.
- Johnson C, Sherwin T, Smythe-Wright D, Shimmield T, Turrell W (2010) Wyville Thomson Ridge Overflow Water: Spatial and temporal distribution in the Rockall Trough. *Deep Sea Res Part I Oceanogr Res Pap* 57:1153–1162.
- de Jong MF, Drijfhout SS, Hazeleger W, van Aken HM, Severijns CA (2009) Simulations of hydrographic properties in the northwestern North Atlantic Ocean in coupled climate models. *J Clim* 22:1767–1786.
- Kanzow T, Zenk W (2014) Structure and transport of the Iceland Scotland Overflow plume along the Reykjanes Ridge in the Iceland Basin. *Deep Sea Res Part I Oceanogr Res Pap* 86:82–93.

- Kieke D, Rhein M (2006) Variability of the overflow water transport in the western subpolar North Atlantic, 1950-97. *J Phys Oceanogr* 36:435–456.
- Langehaug HR, Falck E (2012) Changes in the properties and distribution of the intermediate and deep waters in the Fram Strait. *Prog Oceanogr* 96:57–76.
- Lavín A, Valdés L, Sánchez F, Abaunza P, Forest A, Boucher J, Lazure P, Jegou A-M (2004) The Bay of Biscay: the encountering of the ocean and the shelf. In: *The Sea Volume 14B: The Global Coastal Ocean. Interdisciplinary Regional Studies and Syntheses*. p 935–1003
- Lee A, Ellett D (1967) On the water masses of the Northwest Atlantic Ocean. *Deep Sea Res* 14:183–190.
- MacIsaac KG, Kenchington TJ, Kenchington ELR, Best M (2014) The summer assemblage of large pelagic Crustacea in the Gully submarine canyon: Major patterns. *Deep Sea Res Part II Top Stud Oceanogr* 104:51–66.
- Malmberg S-A, Valdimarsson H, Mortensen J (1996) Long-time series in Icelandic waters in relation to physical variability in the northern North Atlantic. *NAFO Sci Coun Stud* 24:69–80.
- Mastropole D, Pickart RS, Valdimarsson H, Våge K, Jochumsen K, Girton J (2017) On the hydrography of Denmark Strait. *J Geophys Res Ocean* 122:306–321.
- McGrath T, Nolan G, McGovern E (2012) Chemical characteristics of water masses in the Rockall Trough. *Deep Res Part I Oceanogr Res Pap* 61:57–73.
- McKenna C, Berx B, Austin WEN (2016) The decomposition of the Faroe-Shetland Channel water masses using Parametric Optimum Multi-Parameter analysis. *Deep Sea Res Part I Oceanogr Res Pap* 107:9–21.
- Le Moine Bauer S, Stensland A, Daae FL, Sandaa R-A, Thorseth IH, Steen IH, Dahle H (2018) Water masses and depth structure prokaryotic and T4-like viral communities around hydrothermal systems of the Nordic Seas. *Front Microbiol* 9:1–17.
- Mork KA, Drinkwater KF, Jónsson S, Valdimarsson H, Ostrowski M (2014) Water mass exchanges between the Norwegian and Iceland seas over the Jan Mayen Ridge using in-situ current measurements. *J Mar Syst* 139:227–240.
- Oziel L, Sirven J, Gascard J-C (2016) The Barents Sea frontal zones and water masses variability (1980-2011). *Ocean Sci* 12:169–184.
- Palma C, Lillebø AI, Borges C, Souto M, Pereira E, Duarte AC, de Abreu MP (2012) Water column characterisation on the Azores platform and at the sea mounts south of the archipelago. *Mar Pollut Bull* 64:1884–1894.
- Pérez-Hernández MD, Pickart RS, Pavlov V, Våge K, Ingvaldsen R, Sundfjord A, Renner AHH, Torres DJ, Erofeeva SY (2017) The Atlantic Water boundary current north of Svalbard in late summer. *J Geophys Res Ocean* 122:2269–2290.
- Petit T (2018) Characterization of the circulation around, above and across (through fracture zones) the Reykjanes Ridge. Université de Bretagne Occidentale
- Pollard RT, Griffiths MJ, Cunningham SA, Read JF, Pérez FF, Ríos AF (1996) Vivaldi 1991 - A study of the formation, circulation and ventilation of Eastern North Atlantic Central Water. *Prog Oceanogr* 37:167–192.
- Porter M, Inall ME, Hopkins J, Palmer MR, Dale AC, Aleynik D, Barth JA, Mahaffey C, Smeed DA (2016) Glider observations of enhanced deep water upwelling at a shelf break canyon: A mechanism

- for cross-slope carbon and nutrient exchange. *J Geophys Res Ocean* 121:7575–7588.
- Racapé V, Thierry V, Mercier H, Cabanes C (2019) ISOW spreading and mixing as revealed by Deep-Argo Floats launched in the Charlie-Gibbs Fracture Zone. *J Geophys Res Ocean* 124:6787–6808.
- Read JF, Pollard RT (1992) Water masses in the region of the Iceland–Færoes Front. *J Phys Oceanogr* 22:1365–1378.
- Roberts EM, Mienis F, Rapp HT, Hanz U, Meyer HK, Davies AJ (2018) Oceanographic setting and short-timescale environmental variability at an Arctic seamount sponge ground. *Deep Sea Res Part I Oceanogr Res Pap* 138:98–113.
- Rudels B, Eriksson P, Buch E, Budéus G, Fahrbach E, Malmberg S-A, Meincke J, Mälkki P (2003) Temporal switching between sources of the Denmark Strait overflow water. In: *ICES Marine Science Symposia*. p 319–325
- Rudels B, Fahrbach E, Meincke J, Budéus G, Eriksson P (2002) The East Greenland Current and its contribution to the Denmark Strait overflow. *ICES J Mar Sci* 59:1133–1154.
- Rudels B, Schauer U, Björk G, Korhonen M, Pisarev S, Rabe B, Wisotzki A (2013) Observations of water masses and circulation with focus on the Eurasian Basin of the Arctic Ocean from the 1990s to the late 2000s. *Ocean Sci* 9:147–169.
- Schauer U, Muench RD, Rudels B, Timokhov L (1997) Impact of eastern Arctic shelf waters on the Nansen Basin intermediate layers. *J Geophys Res* 102:3371–3382.
- van Sebille E, Baringer MO, Johns WE, Meinen CS, Beal LM, de Jong MF, van Aken HM (2011) Propagation pathways of classical Labrador Sea water from its source region to 26°N. *J Geophys Res* 116:C12027.
- Søiland H, Budgell WP, Knutsen O (2008) The physical oceanographic conditions along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge north of the Azores in June-July 2004. *Deep Sea Res Part II Top Stud Oceanogr* 55:29–44.
- Swift JH, Aagaard K (1981) Seasonal transitions and water mass formation in the Iceland and Greenland seas. *Deep Sea Res* 28A:1107.
- Tang CCL, Ross CK, Yao T, Petrie B, DeTracey BM, Dunlap E (2004) The circulation, water masses and sea-ice of Baffin Bay. *Prog Oceanogr* 63:183–228.
- Turrell WR, Sherwin TJ (2003) A re-examination of the Wyville-Thomson Ridge overflow, and its relevance to fluxes west of Britain. In: *ICES Annual Science Conference 2003*.
- Tychensky A, Le Traon P-Y, Hernandez F, Jourdan D (1998) Large structures and temporal change in the Azores Front during the SEMAPHORE experiment. *J Geophys Res* 103:25,009-25,027.
- Våge K, Pickart RS, Pavlov V, Lin P, Torres DJ, Ingvaldsen R, Sundfjord A, Proshutinsky A (2016) The Atlantic Water boundary current in the Nansen Basin: Transport and mechanisms of lateral exchange. *J Geophys Res Ocean* 121:6946–6960.
- Yashayaev I, Bersch M, van Aken HM (2007) Spreading of the Labrador Sea Water to the Irminger and Iceland basins. *Geophys Res Lett* 34:1–8.